

Composite Materials for the Repair of Concrete Beam

S.Lee, R.S.W.Lee and P. Tong

Advanced Engineering Materials Facility &
Mechanical Engineering Department
The Hong Kong University of Science and Technology
Clear Water Bay, Hong Kong

SUMMARY

An investigation has been carried out to determine the effects of bonding composite patch to cracked concrete beams on the flexural properties and to evaluate repairing procedures for practical application. The overall performance of the repaired beams was better than that of the baseline beam in terms of flexural properties. The wet lay-up long patch gives the best improvement in flexural modulus, yield strength and ultimate strength by 48%, 26% and 14% respectively. Wet lay-up technique gave better mechanical properties than the precured patch. The tested repaired specimens exhibited the predominate shear failure in the concrete and this indicated that shear strengthening of concrete beam could substantially increase the overall structural integrity of the beam.

Keywords: Composite, Concrete Beam, Repair

1. Introduction

Research and field application of steel plates bonded to concrete has been the subject of ongoing research for many years [1-4]. Steel plates bonded to the tension face of concrete beams have been shown to be effective in (i) increasing flexural capacity and (ii) enhancing flexural stiffness thereby reducing deflections and controlling cracking. While steel plates have the advantage of possessing high strength and stiffness properties, they have the disadvantages of being susceptible to corrosion and difficult for adhesive bonding. As an alternative to steel, the use of advanced composite materials for structural rehabilitation shows great potential. The advanced composite materials have high specific strength and stiffness properties. Unlike steel composite materials are unaffected by electrochemical deterioration and can resist the corrosive effects of acids, alkalizes, salts and different aggressive materials under a wide range of temperatures. Published papers [5-8] have described many promising applications of composite materials for a variety of civil structures. In terms of strengthening concrete structures, research efforts have included:

- (1) the bonding of fibre-reinforced plastic composites plates to reinforced concrete beam or slab and improve flexural stiffness and strength,
- (2) the wrapping of concrete columns with composite material jackets to provide the additional flexural and shear strength needed seismic regions,
- (3) the confinement of concrete columns using composite materials, thereby increasing the column axial compression capacity, and
- (4) the wrapping of concrete beams with composite materials to provide additional shear strength.

In this study, work has been carried out to determine the effects of bonding composite patch to cracked concrete beams on the flexural properties and to evaluate repairing procedures for practical application.

2. Test Matrix

It is generally recognized that both the patch material properties and the repairing technique are equally important for any structural repair, because the repairing technique directly affect the repairing cost and the feasibility of using composite materials for the application. The program consists of testing reinforced rectangular concrete beam with and without repairs, see Table 1. The tests were designed to evaluate the effect of the externally bonded, composite fabric reinforcement on the flexural behavior of beam as well as the repairing techniques. The beams were loaded monotonically to failure in four-point bending using an MTS (Model 818) universal testing machine with a loading capacity of 250 KN.

Type	Specimen	No. of Specimen
1	Control	3
2	Pre-cracked	3
3	Repaired with Injected Resin	3
4	Repaired with Precured Composite Patch	3
5	Repaired with Long Patch (wet layup)	3
6	Repaired with Short Patch (wet layup)	3

Table.1 Test Matrix

3. Beam Configuration and Fabrication

Rectangular beams with span length 450 mm and cross-sectional dimensions of 52 mm and 80 mm, the rebar and shear bar reinforcement are the same for beams, see Fig 1. In order to investigate the effects of different repairing techniques and test parameters on the fracture mechanisms of the repaired concrete beams, a total of 18 beams were tested. The detailed are listed and described in the following:

1. Three control beams having only steel rebar and shear bar reinforcement would provide a baseline for determining the effects of crack and different repairing techniques on the flexural properties.
2. Three pre-cracked beams were also tested to determine the effect of crack on the flexural properties.
3. Three cracked beams repaired by injection of a resin into cracks were evaluated to study the effectiveness of the technique in restoring the flexural properties of the beam.
4. Construction on site with difficult accessibility, repaired with pre-cured composite path could be feasible and a set of three specimens was tested in this category.
5. To reduce the processing procedures, reinforced fabric were impregnated with resin and bonded to the pre-cracked beam simultaneously and cured the whole assembly at the same time. Three specimens were prepared with this technique.

6. To evaluate the effect of the patch size on the flexural properties of the repaired beam, the composite path length was reduced by 50 %

Figure 1 Beam Configuration (in mm)

3.1 Beam Fabrication

All steel reinforcements for the concrete beam including the longitudinal rebar (No.4 steel, 8 mm in diameter) and the shear rebars (No.4 steel, 6 mm in diameter) were prefabricated and were positioned in a wooden mould before casting. Strain gauges were also bonded to the longitudinal rebar for monitoring the strain during test, see Figure 2. A concrete mix having a water-to-cement ratio of 0.50 by weight was used to cast the beams. Portland cement was used and the sand size was ranged from 300-600 micro-metre. For the pre-cracked beams, a metal insert length/width/depth =52/0.5/20) was positioned at the mid-span of the beam during the casting and the

Figure (2) Casting Mold for Concrete Beam

insert was removed as to pre-form a crack after the cement started to set. The beams were cast in the Materials Laboratory of Civil and Structural Engineering of the Hong

Kong University of Science and Technology. The cast beams were allowed to cure in a water bath for 28 days as recommended.

4. Composite Materials

The carbon woven used in this study was plain-weave fabric. The fabrics are made up of fibres oriented at 0° and 90° with equal distribution of fibres in each direction. The number of layers of fabric used for the composite patch was 12 plies and was the same as used for the wet lay-up repair. The selected resin should have sufficient strength and stiffness to transfer the shear force between the composite patch and the concrete, and at the same time the resin should be tough to prevent brittle failure of bond between concrete and composite patch. Based on the literature, the resin chosen for pre-impregnating the carbon fabrics was Shell Epikote 815 epoxy resin and the hardener was Shell triamine. For this study, the same resin was used for all the carbon fabric pre-impregnation and bonding of patches to the beams. For the pre-cured patch, a panel of 12 plies 280 mm x 280 mm was lay-up and cured under a vacuum in an autoclave for 4 hour at 50 degree C. The cured panel was machined into patches. The dimension of each patch was approximately 52 mm x 250 mm.

5. Bonding Techniques

Prior to the bonding of the composite patch or wet lay-up of composite materials onto the beam, the concrete surface and the composite patch were sanded with a 200 grit sand paper, creating a somewhat rough surface. After sanding, the bonding surface was cleaned with acetone to remove all sand particles and to ensure that the surfaces were free of contamination

For filling the crack by injecting resin, the resin used was a two parts epoxy supplied by Ciba Geigy (Ciba Epocat 35A/927), which has good mechanical properties as well as possessing low viscosity and relatively long pot life at room temperature. For bonding the composite patch and the wet lay-up of composite onto the beam, Shell 815 epoxy resin was used, see Figure 3. First, the concrete beams were turned upside down and the bonding surfaces of beam and precured composite

Figure (3) Wet Layup Patch

Figure (4) Vacuum Bagging of Whole Assembly

path were coated with premixed resin and placed onto the tension face of the beam. Bond thickness was not specifically controlled, but excess epoxy was squeezed out along the edges of the patch, assuring complete epoxy coverage. The whole assembly was cured an autoclave for 4 hours at 50 degree C with a vacuum, see Figure 4.

6. Instrumentation and Test Procedures

Strain gages were affixed to two locations on the concrete beam and one location internally on the longitudinal steel rebar. Strain gauge was also bonded to the composite patch to monitor the strain during test. The beams were tested in four-point bending over an 450-mm simple span, with the load points 75-mm either side of

Figure (5) Test Set-up

the center, see Figure 5. Mid-span deflections of all beams were measured using the LVDT of the MTS testing machine.

The test procedure consisted of loading all 18 beams monotonically to failure and the loading was displacement-controlled.

7. Test Results and Discussion

Load and deflection data, see Figure 6, collected by the MTS system were used to calculate the flexural modulus and flexural strength of each beam using the following expressions:

Load vs Deflection

Figure (6) Load vs Deflection Curves

$$E_b = \frac{1}{36} \frac{L^3}{Wt^3} \frac{\Delta P}{\Delta \delta} \quad S_b = \frac{LP}{Wt^2}$$

Where

- E_b = Flexural Modulus
- S_b = Flexural strength
- L = Span between two supports
- W = Beam width
- t = Beam thickness
- P = Applied load
- $\Delta P / \Delta \delta$ = Slope of the initial straight line of the load-deflection curve

The results of the 18 tested beams are summarized in Table 2. The failure modes of the controlled beams and the repaired beams are shown schematically in

Figure 7a,b,c,d,e. These results along with the corresponding fracture features are discussed in the sections that follow.

Specimen	Modulus		Yield Strength		Ultimate Strength	
	Result (GPa)	Change (%)	Result (MPa)	Change (%)	Result (MPa)	Change (%)
Base	2.547	---	16.01	---	19.22	---
Cracked	2.233	-12.3	14.94	-6.7	19.01	-1.1
Injected	2.637	3.5	17.35	8.2	20.9	8.7
Short	3.221	26.3	17.48	9.2	20.7	7.7
Com.	3.121	22.5	19.06	19.1	21.33	11.0
Wet	3.787	48.7	20.21	26.2	21.91	14.0

Table (2) A Summary of Test Results

Figure 7 Failure Modes

During the test, each of three control beams began developing flexural tensile cracks in the constant moment region at loads around 14 MPa. At loads around 16MPa, the concrete beams yielded. Finally, each of the three control concrete beams failed in flexure at loads of around 19.2 MPa as a result of the compression concrete crushing. Initially, a vertical crack occurred in the vicinity of the mid-length, and as

the load increased, more vertical cracks developed across the constant moment region, see Figure 7a.

The failure sequence for the pre-cracked beams were similar to the control beams except the modulus and yield strength were 12% and 6.7% respectively lower.

As the applied load increased, the pre-formed crack would gradually extend vertically through the thickness until the beam completely failed, see Figure 7b. The trend of the load against deflection curve was similar to the control beams.

For the beams repaired with the injection of resins, the modulus, yield strength and ultimate strength were slightly increased by 3.5 %, 8.2% and 8.7% respectively as compared with the control beam. The increase in modulus was insignificant and the increases in strengths were small. After the crack was filled and sealed with epoxy, the beam was restored to the original configuration and the flexural modulus was the same as the control beam. Since the epoxy has higher tensile strain than the cement, it was very likely that the initial crack would occur outside of the repaired location, provided that the bond between the epoxy filler and the cement was strong. Therefore, there was a small increase of the yield strength and ultimate strength. Examination of the tested beam revealed that the failure did occur outside of the repaired region, see Figure 7c.

During the test, the general flexural behavior of all the composite patched beams was similar, although the flexural stiffness and final mode of failure varied depending upon the technique. The crack patterns developed were similar for the long patch repaired beam. First cracking usually occurred at a slightly higher load than in the control or pre-cracked beams. Initially, the cracks were vertical, as would be expected for flexural cracks, but later they would bend over in the shear regions. All of the repaired beams failed through the concrete, with cracking initiating from the end of the plate, then proceeding at about a 45 degree or higher up to the internal longitudinal steel rebar, continuing through the concrete, see Figure 7 d-e. This was attributed to the high stiffness of the composite patch, causing the stress in the concrete near the end of the bonded patch to reach the failure stress between the steel rebar reached yield.

For the short wet patched beam, the cracks were developed first under the loading point and propagated along the shear rebar through the thickness. It appears that the composite patch had strengthened the constant moment region but introducing stress concentration in the other region, whereas the crack initially occurred in the vicinity of the shear rebar, see Figure 7d.

The tensile strain of concrete is around 0.001 [9] and this implies that crack would occur initially once the strain on the tension face reached 0.001 and the crack would propagate as the load increased. By reviewing the load vs strain data collected from the longitudinal steel rebar of all the tested beams, the average yield strain was approximately 0.0012 which agreed well with the published data [10], and the steel rebar yielded at a load around 10 kN. The maximum ultimate strain of all tested beams was in the range of 0.0015, which was much lower than the ultimate strain of 0.02 of typical mild steel. Therefore, the steel rebar was in the plastic deformation range but not completely failed.

All beams repaired with composite patch showed at least a modest increase in stiffness, and the wet long patch showed a substantial increase of 48.7%. Yield and ultimate strength increases were moderate except for the wet long patched beam with 26% and 14% increases respectively. This could be attributed to the fact that the wet lay-up fabric could conform more evenly with the bonding surface of the concrete and the variation of the bondline thickness between the patch and the concrete surface could be minimized, thus improving the overall structural integrity of the repaired beam.

8. Conclusions

Repair of concrete beams by using composite materials appears to be a feasible way of restoring and improving the load carrying capacity. Based on the test data and the examination of the tested specimens, the following conclusions are made concerning the mechanical properties and repairing technique:

- The overall performance of the repaired beams was better than that of the baseline beam in terms of flexural properties.
- The wet layup long patch gives the best improvement in flexural modulus, yield strength and ultimate strength by 48%, 26% and 14% respectively.
- The results demonstrated that the long patch performed better than the short patch.
- Examination of the failed specimens revealed that the control and precracked specimens usually exhibited pure bending failure, whereas the repaired specimens exhibited shear failure initiated at the end of the patch.
- Wet layup technique gave better mechanical properties than the precured patch
- The tested repaired specimens exhibited the predominate shear failure in the concrete and this indicated that shear strengthening of concrete beam could substantially increase the overall structural integrity of the beam

Acknowledgements

The financial support from a RIG grant of the Hong Kong University of Science and Technology and from an UGC grant is appreciated. The authors would like acknowledgement the technical support from the staff at the Civil and Structural engineering Laboratory of the Hong Kong University of Science and Technology.

References

1. Lerchenthal, C.H., " Bonded Steel reinforcement for Concrete Slabs", RILEM International Symposium, Synthetic Resins in Building Construction, Paris, 1967, pp.165-73
2. .Sommerard, T., " Swanley's Steel Plate Patch Up", New Civil Engineer, No.247, June 1977, pp.26-7.
3. Mander, R.F., " Use of Resins in Road and Bridge Construction and Repair", The International Journal of Cement Composites, Vol. 3, No. 1. 1981, pp.27-39
4. Jones, R., Swamy, R.N. and Ang. T.H., "Under and Over-reinforced Concrete Beams with Glued Steel Plates", Vol.4, No.1, The International Journal of Cement Composites and Lightweight Concrete. Vol.4, No.1, February, 1982, pp.19-32.
5. Swamy, R.N., Jones, R. and Bloxham, J.W. Structural Behaviour of Reinforced concrete beams strengthened by epoxy-bonded steel plate", Structural Engineering Part A Vol. 65. No.2, 1987, pp 59-68.
6. Ballinger, C.A. " Development of Composites for Civil Engineering Advanced Composite Materials in Civil Engineering Structures", ASCE, Las Vegas, Nevada, 1991, pp.228-301.
7. Head, P.R. " Design Methods and Bridge Forms for the Cost Effective Use of Advanced Composites in Bridges", Advanced Composite Materials in Bridges and Structures, CSCE, Sherbrooke, Canada, 1992, pp.15-30.
8. Saadatmanesh, H. and Ehsani, M.R. " Application of Fibre Composites in Civil Engineering", Proceeding 7th Structures Conference. ASCE, 1989, pp.526-535.
9. Mindess, S. and Young, J.F., "Concrete", Prentice-Hall, Inc. Englewood Cliffs, 1981.
10. Kumar Mehta, P. and Monteiro, P.J.M., " Concrete Structure, Properties and Materials" 2nd edition, Prentice Hall, Inc., Englewood Cliffs. 1993